

East Lake Street: The Story of Latine Economic Development

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Abstract

Valle, Arredondo, and Fowler analyze the sudden growth and development of Latine businesses on East Lake Street in Minneapolis, Minnesota that occurred between the 1990s and 2020. The authors propose that Latine-owned businesses flourished on the East Lake Street due to significant support and opportunities provided by cultural hubs and nonprofit organizations existing within the neighborhood. Their findings suggest that nonprofit developmental organizations have a significant influence on the economic development of an ethnic enclave.

East Lake Street: The Story of Latine Economic Development

Lake Street is a prominent, well-traveled street in Minneapolis that has experienced significant changes over the last few decades; with major shifts in racial and class demographics, business patterns, and investment. Today, East Lake Street is characterized by the multitude of restaurants — most Mexican — and cultural vibrancy. East Lake Street, however, has only looked like this in recent years: it is now home to a unique concentration of Latine-owned businesses over multiple blocks, surrounded on either side by Uptown – a more White, upper-class neighborhood – to the West, and Highway 55 to the East. Within a quarter mile of East Lake Street, 49% of the population is Latine, 18% of people are living in poverty, and 62% of residents work in “essential” jobs, as defined by the Department of Homeland Security Cybersecurity & Infrastructure Security Agency (Hennepin County, 2022). Despite the high concentration of poverty, the business community thrives on Lake Street. This business community can be attributed to many different elements primarily built around the opportunities that Minnesota, and more specifically Lake Street, create for Latine people – especially those who are noncitizens. Before discussing the elements that changed Lake Street, it is necessary to understand how these businesses developed in the first place.

Minnesota has a fairly low Hispanic population of only 5.49% (World Population Review, 2023), which is a stark contrast compared to 49% on Lake Street. This difference raises the question; what about East Lake Street attracted this specific population, and allowed it to flourish – especially in contrast to the demographics of the surrounding neighborhoods and general area? In our research, we aimed to investigate the source of the concentration of Mexican-owned businesses on Lake Street, the shift in the racial demographics in the area, and what opportunities resulted in the current thriving cultural centers. By talking with members of

the Lake St. Council planners involved with Mercado Central and Midtown Global Market; and gathering census data and other field observations, we propose that Latine-owned businesses flourish in this neighborhood due to the copious support and opportunities provided by cultural hubs and nonprofit organizations existing within the ethnic enclave on Lake Street.

Prior to the 1960s and 1970s, Lake Street was primarily home to Scandinavian and Greek immigrants. After the increased dependence on cars and the replacement of the street car system with highways, many European immigrants left Lake Street to relocate to suburban areas. Businesses turned into vacancies, and Lake Street's business culture plummeted. In order to combat the regression and stimulate business initiatives, various development organizations were formed in the following decades. The main organizations relating to this neighborhood analysis are the Lake Street Council (est.1968), the Latino Economic Development Center (est.1999), and the Neighborhood Development Center (NDC, est.1993). Lake Street Council became a business network more than just a nonprofit, as it prioritized bringing business owners together, encouraging more people to come to Lake Street, and improving the business corridor. Now, they prioritize building long-standing relationships with business owners, providing them with opportunities where possible. Other nonprofits and urban development organizations followed suit, such as the Latino Economic Development Center (LEDC) which helped create the Mercado Central, and now provides classes, workshops, assistance, and loans to Latine-owned businesses (Latino Economic Development Center LEDC, n.d.). The NDC was also a key player in the development on Lake Street – they work with businesses on marketing, event management, and budgeting; as well as with aid in the development of the Midtown Global Market. By the time these nonprofits began setting up shop and supporting the surrounding community, the demographics had changed immensely. Mexican immigrants had moved into the neighborhoods

on Lake Street and also bought empty lots along the street. The combination of organizations like the NDC and the LEDC, the leadership of community organizers such as Juan Linares, and the influx of Mexican immigrants led to the blossoming of immigrant-owned businesses. The most prominent of these developments is Mercado Central, established in 1997 by three immigrant entrepreneurs who run La Loma Tamales, Taqueria la Hacienda, and La Perla Tortillas. The Mercado served as a catalyst for the development of Lake Street, fueling investments to the area by nonprofit organizations, entrepreneurs, and public urban planners (Visit Lake Street, n.d.).

In this paper, we will include context about the neighborhood's history, characteristics, and change in demographics; drawing on our own observations, existing research and literature on ethnic enclaves, interviews we personally conducted, and census data. We will analyze the relevant data, comparing the racial makeup of Lake Street in the 1990's to the 2020's; as well as discuss the formation and impact of cultural centers in the neighborhood such as Mercado Central and Midtown Global Market. With our thorough research into East Lake Street's businesses, we aim to paint a portrait of what made the area so culturally vibrant.

Detailed Presentation of the Area

In order to collect accurate data, we define our area of interest as the stretch of Lake Street between Chicago Avenue and Highway 55. This section of Lake Street is characterized by an abundance of Mexican-owned businesses: mostly restaurants, but the area includes clothing shops and other retail stores as well. This block includes Mercado Central, Midtown Global Market, and close to a dozen other restaurants. East Lake Street is typically characterized as the stretch of Lake Street between Pillsbury Avenue and Cedar Ave. (Fig. 1); our area of interest is thus a small section of East Lake Street, represented by the dotted red line in *Figure 1*. We chose to do this in favor of more specific census data, a smaller scope of

interest, and the ability to look more closely at the area with the highest concentration of restaurants and businesses – including Mercado Central (Fig. 5) and Midtown Global Market (Fig. 6). We also are only looking at Lake Street itself – not the surrounding neighborhoods. We chose to do this because the surrounding neighborhoods are predominantly residential, and the analysis of residential data is beyond the scope of this paper.

Figure 1

East Lake Street Defined–Area of interest in red dashes

Note. Figure retrieved from "East Lake Street" by Mendez (n.d.) on the Meet Minneapolis website. Available at <https://www.minneapolis.org/cultural-districts/districts/east-lake-street/>

In order to track the changes in the Latine population along with other demographic races, we looked at decennial census data organized by the IPUMS National Historical Geographic Information System. We chose census tracts which included Mercado Central and

Midtown Market to show correlations between changes in demographics and changes in business ownership. We were able to find two 1990 census tracts¹, 72 and 29 (Fig. 4), that matched up very closely to census tract 1258 (Fig. 3) of the 2020 census. Both share Chicago Avenue South as the western border and East Lake Street as the southern border, but the northern and eastern borders vary. The northern border of tract 1258 is East 25th Street, while the northern border for tracts 72 and 79 is one street further north on East 24th Street. The eastern border of tract 1258 is Bloomington Avenue, while the eastern border of tracts 72 and 79 is South 17th Avenue (United States Census Bureau) which is two streets east. The results do have a slight margin of error, but our results are dramatic enough to show that there has been an increase in the number of people who are Hispanic or Latine in the area of focus. As shown in *Figure 2*, the area went from a Latine population of 162 in 1990 to 1,883 in 2020; meanwhile, the general population of the area only changed from 5,239 in 1990 to 5,208 in 2020. This shows a trend of non-Hispanics moving out and Hispanics moving into the area, suggesting that the increase in Mexican and Latine-owned businesses is correlated with the demographic changes in the region (Steven Manson, Jonathan Schroeder, David Van Riper). The change in demographics within this area reflects the impact that neighborhood programs and initiatives have had on the population and dynamics of Lake Street.

Figure 2

Population Demographics in 1990 and 2020

Year	Census Tract	Total Population	Hispanic or Latine Population	White Population	Black or African	American Indian & Alaska	Asian, Native Hawaiian, & Other Pacific Islander
1990	72 & 79	5239	162 (3.1%)	2266 (43.3%)	822 (15.7%)	1536 (29.3%)	556 (10.6%)
2020	1258	5208	1883 (36.2%)	1248 (24.0%)	1803 (34.6%)	239 (4.6%)	93 (1.8%)

Note. Data retrieved from the *IPUMS National Historical Geographic Information System (NHGIS), Version 18.0 [dataset]*, authored by Steven Manson, Jonathan Schroeder, David Van Riper, Katherine Knowles, Tracy Kugler, Finn Roberts, and Steven Ruggles. Copyright 2023 by IPUMS, Minneapolis, MN. Available at <http://doi.org/10.18128/D050.V18.0>.

Figure 3

Image of the 2020 census tract used in the demographic evaluation

Note. Retrieved from the United States Census Bureau (2021, February 8). Available at https://www2.census.gov/geo/maps/DC2020/PL20/st27_mn/censustract_maps/c27053_hennepin.

Figure 4

Image of the 1990 census tract used in the demographic evaluation

Note. Retrieved from the United States Census Bureau (2002, June 10). Available at https://www2.census.gov/geo/maps/trt1990/st27_Minnesota/27053_Hennepin/.

Figure 5

Mercado Central (own photo)

Figure 6

Midtown Global Market (own photo)

East Lake Street, recently deemed a cultural district, or a marginalized area of rich cultural identity, in 2020 by the Minneapolis government (Bui, n.d.), stands out in comparison to the rest of the neighborhoods surrounding it. Walking or driving down the street, one may see many unique aspects of Lake Street, namely Latine and East African storefronts, murals, and two marketplaces: Mercado Central and Midtown Global Market, as seen in *Figure 5* and *Figure 6*, respectively. Midtown Global Market occupies a building initially built in 1928 when it functioned as a Sears building. It was then vacant from 1994-2005 when Lake Street's demographics were vastly different from those of other neighborhoods in Minneapolis. East Lake Street is lined with dozens of Mexican storefronts and restaurants, with the Mercado Central and Midtown Global Market also providing an additional influx of Mexican business owners and giving a home to businesses with smaller stands and kitchens to cluster in one spot. While the

two major cultural centers seem to be similar in terms of model and role served to the neighborhood, they are actually very different in terms of operation and formation.

Figure 7

Hispanic Businesses on Lake Street (own photo)

Figure 8

Mexican Business on Lake Street (own photo)

Evaluation of Evidence and Methods

In researching Lake Street and what created the strong Latine population we see today, we visited Lake Street multiple times and met with planners from a few of the major organizations involved with businesses on Lake Street. Based on our observations and interviews, we then accessed existing literature and studies on ethnic enclaves similar to Lake Street to describe the environment. We met with Juan Linares, a founding member of Mercado Central, who was able to provide context about the history and role of Mercado Central within the community. Mercado Central began its formation process in 1992 and first opened its doors in 1999. While speaking with Juan Linares, he recounted that in the early formation stages of the Mercado, organizers conducted interviews, usually in Spanish, with community members. These interviews posed questions such as, “What do you think you do well?”, “Have you ever felt or thought that you could start a business in your house or neighborhood?”, “What would you do?”, “Why haven’t you started it?”, “What’s stopping you?”, and others geared towards finding out what talents community members possessed. We found that this opportunity that foreign-born residents had to demonstrate and express their talents facilitated the creation of a business community, for it removed barriers that normally would prevent immigrants from starting businesses. Eduardo Barrera, Real Estate Development Manager of the NDC, explained that when “the Mercado Central was envisioned, most of the Latino community viewed this as an opportunity to establish themselves in the community – or they were already established – and they saw this as an opportunity to begin a journey in entrepreneurship”; revealing that Mercado Central served as a mechanism for immigrants to build a business community on Lake Street (Barrera & Temali, 2023).

During this development process, Mercado Central worked closely with the NDC which organized a 11-week entrepreneur training and provided additional aid with legal matters, sales

and marketing, business planning and development, overall bookkeeping, and more. In our joint interview with Mihailo Temali, founder of the NDC, and Barrera, we learned more about the NDC and other organizers' objectives throughout the planning of Mercado Central. They explained that community organizers aimed to develop a relationship with the residents, and Barrera emphasized how big of a component trust is for noncitizen community members, as they are in an unfamiliar country with few connections. One major step in the NDC's process was getting to know individuals to build relationships, and trust, and identify problems outside of entrepreneurship that could help the community succeed. Temali, founder of the NDC, expressed that, "Everything [the NDC has] done anywhere, not just the Latino community, it always starts with a community group that people trust enough to come forward" (Barrera & Temali, 2023). Through Barrera and Temali's statements, we can infer that one of the reasons why the immigrant community thrived on Lake Street was because of these community groups within East Lake Street that sought to strengthen relationships and trust with the residents that they served.

Throughout its operation, Mercado Central has helped its business partners access over \$277,000 in business loans, and in its first year brought in over \$2 million in sales. It supports about 40 businesses and has hired over 70 people (The Asset-Based Community Development Institute). Finally, the market helped people gain access to critical resources for managing life as a new immigrant, including the resources required to start a business. These unique opportunities, combined with the reduced rent provided to business owners operating within the Mercado Central or Midtown Market, have turned the centers into incubators for businesses on Lake Street. Many businesses that began in these markets are able to expand beyond the buildings they started in. Out of businesses that initially opened in 1999, 54% are still in the Mercado, 22% moved, 22% opened second locations, and 8% expanded outside the Mercado.

This last percentage includes La Perla Tortillas, which Juan Linares explained started as a small business within the Mercado Central, but has now opened up operations in another building nearby Lake Street. They still keep part of their business inside Mercado Central but have had to expand to increase their production capacity. La Perla Tortillas now sells tortillas to major retailers all across Minnesota and, more recently, in Canada. Additionally, Mercado Central emphasizes keeping business local and family-owned. La Reyna De Los Jugos is a company that sells a variety of juices in a space no larger than 50 square feet. The business started off run by an immigrant Latina woman and is now run by her four daughters.

The large population of Mexican families and businesses on East Lake St. constitutes an area expounded as an ethnic enclave, defined by the National Library of Medicine as an area in which a specific ethnic group is tightly clustered, as well as being socially and economically distinct from the majority surrounding groups. While ethnic enclaves have historically been viewed as having a negative impact on immigrants integrating into a new country due to a continued separation from the cultural majority, recent studies have shown that they can actually have positive economic outcomes for refugees or immigrants. Choosing residence in an ethnic enclave can result in higher chances of employment within the first five years of arrival in a host country, due to the sharing of culture, language, knowledge, and nationality (Stanford News, 2019); likewise, ethnic clusters are generally believed to provide a protected market for goods and services produced by minority businesses for other minorities that promote increased entrepreneurship in the area (Clark, 2015). In other words, the money spent on Latine goods by Latines goes directly back to the community. These findings are reflected in the Lake Street community, as the neighborhood is more welcoming to Spanish-speaking employees, customers, and businesses with food or other cultural goods from Mexico and other Latin American countries. An 'ethnic enclave entrepreneur' is a term used to describe businesses that employ

co-ethnic workers, are clustered within ethnic enclaves, and serve predominantly their own ethnic community. Entrepreneurship becomes a possibility for immigrants in ethnic enclaves due to existing social networks which can facilitate the construction of smaller-scale enterprises and take advantage of the surrounding ethnic community. Entrepreneurship and self-employment are common career paths among immigrants, but according to Ken Clark, this pattern cannot only be taken as a sign of economic health but might instead be symptomatic of discrimination by the majority community (Clark, 2015). This means that immigrants are often forced into roles of self-employment due to limited social mobility and lack of opportunities provided by the majority, and many struggle to find employment even within the fields they are trained and qualified for. For example, qualifications an immigrant might have obtained from their country of origin may not be recognized in the United States, or other barriers such as language might pose an obstacle to getting work (Bloch & McKay, 2016). Self-employment thus allows an opportunity for immigrants to generate income without having to navigate a discriminatory hiring environment or customer base. Co-ethnic networks and ethnic enclaves provide the support that makes starting a business a far more feasible undertaking.

Lake Street, however, is different in some ways from the dominant U.S. ethnic enclave narrative. In many cases of ethnic enclaves throughout the United States, the opportunities provided by being an ethnic enclave entrepreneur only last a few years, before the market begins to narrow and existing businesses are crowded out by new entrants (Bloch & McKay, 2016). Matt Kazinka, program developer for the Lake St. Council reported that sharing of language and background has had positive long-term community impacts, and resulted in more Latine residents coming to Lake Street to live among those who share their language and culture. Works of Clark, Bloch, McKay, along with other existing literature on ethnic enclaves and entrepreneurship conclude that trust is the fundamental building block of successful ethnic

enclaves, and our personal interviews corroborate this finding. Temali also talked about the importance of working within all aspects of a community – not just business. This includes education, housing, religion, and health; along with the NDC’s priority in continued investment in existing and long-standing businesses. The importance of building close relationships with business owners on Lake Street came up in all the interviews we conducted, and as a result of this, the statistics of Mercado Central’s business retention and growth since 1999 indicate the pattern of immigrant business owners being crowded out is not present on East Lake Street.

Conclusion

In our work along East Lake Street, our conversations, research, interviews, and observations have painted a clear story of how the culturally vibrant community came to be. Our observations indicate that the success of the ethnic enclave on Lake Street can be largely attributed to the many nonprofit organizations that have provided opportunities for existing businesses to flourish and new businesses to get their footing. Incubators like Mercado Central and Midtown Global Market which offer reduced rent and smaller spaces allow for businesses with less capital to thrive, and build their business until they decide to move or expand their franchise. The support offered by these organizations is major for any start-up business: but especially for immigrants seeking a community and stability, and the emphasis on relationships and trust within the Lake Street Council and NDC means ethnic enclave entrepreneurs are supported in the long term, not solely for the first few years after immigrating. Having organizations that focused specifically on Latine economic success and development offered additional help for immigrants and those of Latin origin; fostering a bustling and successful business community full of immigrant entrepreneurs. Finally, there is a lot to be said for finding a community that speaks the same language and provides food, music, and other cultural goods from home in addition to the opportunities provided by the organizations focused in the area.

While our analysis and research do include many valuable takeaways, it is also important to note some of the shortcomings of our findings. Eduardo Barrera from the NDC explained to us that the story can sometimes be more valuable than the numbers themselves; but the first and most obvious flaw is that we have a lack of quantitative data and analysis of the area of interest. For example, information on changes in land prices over time or exact numerical differences in the rent at Mercado Central/Midtown Global Market in comparison to surrounding storefronts could have added much depth to our findings. Another shortcoming is that we only interviewed and worked with community development centers, rather than with individual businesses and community members themselves. While the information we gathered from these centers was crucial to our findings, there is much value to be added from the individual experiences and stories of Lake Street community members. Lake Street is a rich and diverse space, and as such it would take much more time and research to depict its story in its entirety.

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Footnotes

¹It is important to note that since the boundaries of census tracts often change with each decennial census, it was not possible to find two census tracts that exactly lined up between the two periods.